

METHODS OF REFLECTIVE TECHNOLOGY IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSES

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***Abstract.** This article is devoted to the description methods of reflective technology in foreign language classes. The article analyzes various points of view on the definition of the concept of “reflection”, considered by scientists of philosophy, psychology, and pedagogy, and proposes the author’s definition of reflection from the point of view of methods of teaching foreign languages. Reflection on the purpose of implementation is described: reflection on the mood and emotional state of students, reflection on the assimilation of the content of educational material by students, reflection on the form of student activity. The practical application of the reflection stage in foreign language lessons is proposed based on the use of such techniques as “Color Test”, “Reflective Screen”, “Method five 5 fingers”.*

***Key words.** Methodology, technique, reflection, “Color Test”, “Reflective Screen”, “Method five 5 fingers”, foreign language.*

Introduction. Reflexive technology is a technology that promotes the formation, development, improvement and consolidation of students’ knowledge, skills, abilities and relevant competencies in acquisition of foreign languages. The American scientist Pierre Teilhard de Chardin defines reflection as the ability acquired by consciousness to focus on oneself and master oneself as an object that has its own specific stability and its own specific meaning - the ability not just to know, but to know oneself; not just know, but know that you know [5]. In the book “Psychology of Human Development” we find the following definition of reflection: “Reflection is such a specifically human ability that allows a person to make his thoughts, emotional states, his actions and relationships, in general his

whole self, the subject of special consideration (analysis and evaluation) and practical transformation (change and development)” [4].

From a philosophical point of view, the essence of the concept of “reflection” comes down to three main processes: as a process of turning back; as a process of self-knowledge by a person of his own mental qualities and state; as a process of understanding social reality in the process of socialization [1].

In pedagogy V.V. Davydov, V.A. Slavenin, T.I. Shamova consider reflection as a pedagogical definition. They describe it as a professional ability, associate it with professional competence, and explore the role of reflection in the successful activities of teachers in a multidimensional way. L. Zankov, I. Yakimanskaya consider reflection as an element of developmental teaching technology, which is successfully used in school practice [6].

Thus, in pedagogy, reflection is considered as a process of thinking and activity. Pedagogical reflection is the integration of processes of research into one’s activities, which enriches professional and pedagogical experience.

A study of the literature on reflection allows us to conclude that reflection is studied as a philosophical category and is also studied by such disciplines as pedagogy and psychology. Based on scientists’ definitions of reflection, we have developed our own definition. In our opinion, reflection is one of the main stages of the lesson, which involves a process of interrelated activities between the teacher and students to acquire knowledge, skills and abilities, during which students independently assess their state, emotions, knowledge, analyze the information received, the results of their activities on the subject being studied. Thus, from a methodological point of view, reflection is the process of organizing a lesson, where schoolteachers need to develop the reflective competence of students, increase the need for discussions on the topics being studied, and solving analytical, logical and creative problems.

Main part. According to the purpose of the conducting, there are three types of reflection: reflection of the mood and emotional state of students, reflection on

the assimilation of the content of educational material by students, reflection on the form of student activity [2].

Reflection of the mood and emotional state of students - it is a type of reflection that contributes to the formation of a favorable microclimate in the classroom. It is advisable to conduct such reflection at the beginning of the lesson in order to establish emotional contact or at the end as a stage of summing up the lesson. Reflection on the mood and emotional state of students is multivariate and is not difficult to carry out. It assesses the emotional mood of students and their perception of educational material. This is a reflection from the categories “liked/disliked”, “interesting/boring”, and “it was fun/sad”.

Reflection on the assimilation of the content of educational material by students - it is a type of reflection at the end of a lesson, where it is important for the teacher not only to find out and understand the emotional state of students at the end of the lesson, but also how productive the lesson has become for them, how firmly the students have mastered the content of the educational material. Students need to evaluate their activity in the lesson, the usefulness and interestingness of the forms of presenting knowledge, the fascination of the lesson, and teamwork.

Reflection on the form of student activity – it is a reflection, which contributes to the analysis of students’ activities in the lesson, identifying existing problems on the topic being studied, used at the stage of checking homework, defending project, research and independent work, at the stage of consolidating the material. This reflection can be collective, group, frontal, or individual.

Let's look at examples of using methods of reflective technology in foreign language classes. When conducting “Reflection of the mood and emotional state of students”, you can use the “Color Test” technique by Max Luscher. At the end of the lesson, students are asked to determine what their own mood was during the color lesson, using the characteristics of colors by the Swiss psychologist Max Luscher. The Luscher test is based on the assumption that the choice of color often

reflects the subject's focus on a certain activity, mood, functional state and the most stable personality traits. Characteristics of colors according to Max Luscher include 4 primary and 4 additional colors. Primary colors - blue, green, red and yellow - reflect the basic psychological needs of people: satisfaction with something, attachment to something, self-confidence, activity, desire for something or, expectation of something good, need for success:

- 1) blue - symbolizes calmness, contentment;
- 2) green - a sense of confidence, perseverance, sometimes stubbornness;
- 3) red - symbolizes willpower, aggressiveness, offensive tendencies, excitement;
- 4) yellow - activity, desire to communicate, expansiveness, cheerfulness.

Additional colors: purple, brown, black, gray. They symbolize negative tendencies: anxiety, stress, fear, grief:

- 1) purple – restless, anxious mood, close to disappointment;
- 2) brown – passivity, anxiety and uncertainty;
- 3) black – sad mood, denial, protest;
- 4) gray – isolation, sadness [3].

At the end of the test, you can conduct a question-and-answer conversation: Did you know previously, what do colors influence our emotional state? Do you agree with Max Luscher's theory, prove why? Have you noticed the influence of color on a person's mood, if so, give examples?

Conducting "Reflection on the assimilation of the content of educational material by students" you can use the "Reflective screen" technique. The guys in a circle speak in one sentence, justifying their answers, choosing the beginning of a phrase from the reflective screen on the board: 1. Today I found out ... 2. It was interesting, namely...

3. It was difficult to learn a new topic because...4. I acquired knowledge...5. I was surprised...

Conducting “Reflection on the form of student activity” we suggest using the techniques “Five Fingers method”. This is a simple and accessible technique in which each finger of the hand is assigned one of the controlled parameters of the quality of achieving the goal. The “Five Finger Method” was developed by the German writer, lecturer, author of books on personal and financial effectiveness, including “The Path to Financial Freedom”, “A Dog Named Money”, “The Laws of Winners” Bodo Schaefer, and a leading expert on time management in Germany and Europe, author of the bestsellers “More Time for Essentials”, “If You’re in a Hurry, Take Your Time”, “The Boomerang Principle: More Time for Happiness” Lothar Zeiwert [7].

The “Five-finger method” is that, using the palm of the right hand, using the first letters of the names of the fingers, students remember the parameters on the basis of which control is carried out and answer questions, and the wording of the questions can be changed by the teacher.

“**L**” (little finger) – thoughts, knowledge, information: what new did I learn today? What knowledge did you acquire? What experience did I have today?

“**U**” (unnamed) – proximity to the goal: what did I do today and what did I achieve?

“**M**” (medium) – state of mind, mood: what was my mood, mood? What was associated with positive emotions?

“**I**” (indicative) – service, help, cooperation: how did I help others today? Have my relationships with others improved?

“**T**” (thumb) – vigor, health, physical condition: what have I done today for my health?

Conclusion. All of the above allows us to conclude that reflection is a process of constant analysis of one’s own activities and its results. The use of reflection techniques in a foreign language lesson makes the process of teaching languages more effective and interesting, allowing you to analyze the successes of students,

determine their weaknesses and strengths, promoting awareness of the learning goal, which is a motivational factor for learning a foreign language.

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